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Research Article

STUDY TO KNOW TREATMENT OF INFECTED NON-UNION TIBIA BY INTERCALARY BONE TRANSPORT

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Abstract:

Objective: To evaluate the efficacy of Ilizarov ring fixator with intercalary bone transport in the infected non-union tibia treatment.

Study Design: A quasi-experimental study.

Place and Duration: In the Orthopaedic department of Capital Hospital Islamabad for two-year duration from March 2017 to March 2019.

Methodology: Sixteen patients with non-unionized infected tibia (type IV osteomyelitis Lax / Cierney), all male and age range of 20-60 years with 32 years mean age; The most common cause was open fracture and the most common site was lower 1/3. In infected tibia with sinus drainage, a wound smear was performed for sensitivity and culture and a sinogram was performed. Sequestrectomy and debridement were performed leaving gap between 2 and 8 cm (mean 4.5 cm) and Ilizarov ring fixator. A navigation cable was passed through the medial malleolus, the irrigation system was installed, and the wound was sealed in a one layer. A proximal metaphyseal corticotomy was performed. For five days, normal saline of two to three liters and irrigation with proper antibiotics were started. On the fifth day, the removal of irrigation system was done, and transport began. Patients endured partially loaded until soft tissue healing occurred. Transport was carried out at a speed of 1 mm / day with the navigation cable until the coupling was achieved. After healing of soft tissues, it allowed to support all weight; Physiotherapy of the ankle and knee started from the first day. After 2-3 weeks of coupling; navigation cable was disconnected. 12 to 27 months was the follow-up time with 16 months mean.

Results: In each case, the union was achieved during the removal of the frame, ie between 8-13 months. The union duration at the site of placement ranged from 3.5 months to 6 months with 4.5 months mean. The bone grafting required in 2 patients at the insertion site. In a regenerated state, it was broken due to the plaster-treated fall. All subjects were gratified except one 60-year-old patient with knee osteoarthritis in severe stage. In all patients; Pin tract infection occurred and was inactivated by proper antibiotics. Infection was reduced in all cases except two cases who underwent local flap debridement.

Conclusion: Intercalary bone transplantation with the Ilizarov ring fixator is the preferred treatment for non-union of the loose and infected tibia without discrepancy in the length of the leg.

Key Words: Ilizarov ring fixator, infection, non-unionized tibia, navigation cable, external fixator.

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INTRODUCTION:

Non-union gap and Infection are the challenges that orthopaedic surgeons have to tackle worldwide¹. The infected non-union is a Cierny IV osteomyelitis according to the definition; this means that before and after debridement the fracture was unstable². Radical debridement, flap, bone graft, etc. Several methods have been tried to solve this issue. None is satisfactory and morbidity during treatment is high³. Debridement and sequestrectomy result in large gaps that are problematic to manage by conventional methods⁴. Interlaced nail (ILN) or Internal fixation with a dynamic compression plate (DCP) is not possible due to gap in the outside region, the imperfect bone density and quality and, above all with infection⁵. Under these circumstances, the preferred treatment is external fixator, especially of the Ilizarov ring fixator⁶. With this device, the transport of the soft tissues is possible with the interspersed bone transplantation, which leads to the removal of the void and soft tissue coating without any differences or stiffness in the length of the leg⁷.

In this method, in the proximal segment 2 rings and 2 rings in the distal portion of this fixator and one ring in the segment to be transported. In most cases, the navigation cable is installed to route the

transmission through the medial malleolus to the docking area⁸. A proximal metaphysical corticotomy was performed. The normal saline wound irrigation system with appropriate antibiotics plays a decisive role in eradicating infection. With this technique, the infected tissue and the involved bone resected, and the resulting defect can be rebuilt⁹.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This quasi-experimental study was held in the Orthopaedic department of Capital Hospital Islamabad for two-year duration from March 2017 to March 2019. All sixteen male patients with non-unionized tibia (Lax / Cierny type IV osteomyelitis) infected were treated. The mean duration of infection and association was two years. The most common cause is the tibia open fracture and the most common place is 1/3 lower. In each case, swabs were sent for culture and sensitivity and a sinogram was performed. After preparation, debridement and Sequestrectomy were performed and Ilizarov ring fixator was applied, the transplant set left a gap of 2 and 8 cm with 4.5 cm mean. A proximal metaphysical corticotomy was performed and through the medial malleolus a navigation cable was passed (Figure 1).

An irrigation system was installed and sealed in a single layer. For five days, normal saline of two to three liters and irrigation with proper antibiotics were started. On the fifth day, the removal of irrigation system was done and transport began. The patient endured partially loaded for about three weeks until the soft tissue healed. The proper antibiotics were administered. Transport was carried

out on the navigation cable at a speed of 1 mm / day with full weight support until the connection was made (Figures 3 and 4). Ankle and Knee physiotherapy was continued from the first day. The navigation cable was disconnected after coupling, but the patient remained in the frame until regeneration was consolidated and union occurred at the non-union site (Figure 5).

After removing the frame, the plate was applied on the knee for two weeks without heavy load, and then applied with the weight of the splint for two weeks. The gait training was recommended, and Patients were followed-up for at least six months. (Figure 6).

RESULTS:

In each case, the union was achieved during the dismantling of the frame, ie between 8-13 months (Fig. 7). The union time at the site of attachment ranged from 3.5 months to 6 months with average 4.5 months as shown in Table 1.

No.	Age	Site of Non-Union Tibia	No. of Previous Operations	Duration of Union at Docking site
1	22 years	Junction of middle and distal 1/3	4	
2	21 years	Mid-diaphyseal	1	4.5 months
3	26 years	Junction of middle and distal 1/3	3	4.3 months
4	32 years	Junction of middle and distal 1/3	1	3.6 months
5	20 years	Mid-diaphyseal	1	3.2 months
6	36 years	Junction of middle and distal 1/3	2	5.4 months
7	51 years	Junction of middle and distal 1/3	2	6.0 months
8	31 years	Junction of middle and distal 1/3	3	4.4 months
9	26 years	Mid-diaphyseal	1	5.2 months
10	23 years	Mid-diaphyseal	2	4.8 months
11	32 years	Junction of middle and distal 1/3	4	3.5 months
12	60 years	Junction of middle and distal 1/3	1	5.4 months
13	45 years	Mid-diaphyseal	3	4.9 months
14	34 years	Junction of middle and distal 1/3	1	4.3 months
15	20 years	Junction of middle and distal 1/3	3	3.8 months
16	33 years	Junction of middle and distal 1/3	2	4.0 months

Table I. Patients' Data and Duration of Union

In a regenerated state, it was broken due to the plaster-treated fall. All patients were gratified excluding for a 60-year-old man who developed osteoarthritis of the knee in severe stage. In all patients; Pin tract infection occurred and was inactivated by proper antibiotics. Infection was reduced in all cases except two cases who underwent local flap debridement.

DISCUSSION:

The long-term infected union and non-union gap is a difficult problem for orthopaedists and difficult to treat. It mostly results in permanent deformity, contracture and chronic infection and in the worst cases, unusable limb¹⁰. Many approaches have been used to deal with this problem, For example, local flap, radial debridement, bone graft, muscle flap, spongy allograft, tibiofibular synostosis, fibrin mixed with antibiotics, vascularized bone transplantation and microvascular flaps¹¹. They all enhanced the results, but none fully resolved this clinical condition. The Ilizarov ring stabilizer offers a choice of distraction, bone transport and compression and is operative in treating non-conjugation with infected tibia, where other treatment fail. The weight support and functioning of the joints during management is an advantage that cannot be matched with another technique¹².

The Ilizarov device is axially flexible and because the weight bearing forces are applied directly to the bone ends, the maintenance of the weight bearing function of the limb becomes a prerequisite for the success of the method. Instead of rigidity rather than union or fracture, cyclic axial telescopic mobility is an essential requirement for the formation of a repair callus. Ilizarov experimentally showed that when gradual distraction tension was applied to the corticectomy site, vascularization of all limbs increased, which improved the ability of the ends of the bone to join¹³.

In a study by Tranquilli et al. In 20 patients without tibial association in Italy, the result was union in all cases; the average duration of unions is 4.5 months. In another study, Marsh et al. demonstrated a high level of patient satisfaction in 40 of 46 non-unionized cases treated with the Ilizarov method¹⁴. In their study, Menon et al. Concluded that the Ilizarov ring fixator had a function of retaining nails in the non-diaphragm union of the non-diaphragm-resistant long bone, and that this method could provide high binding rates in cases where other methods failed. For example, various modifications have been made to improve the efficacy of treatment with the Ilizarov method and patient acceptability¹⁵. The implementation time of the framework is a disadvantage, but when all other treatment methods fail, this technique is probably the only alternative and only hope for many suffering patients, although

patient compliance is important for a successful result.

CONCLUSION:

The result obtained from this study is that the preferred treatment method for bone intercalary transplantation interspersed with the Ilizarov ring fixator for lax infected non-union of tibia without leg length discrepancy.

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